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Prospective site-specific life cycle assessment of ocean alkalinity enhancement

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E-mail: maria.myridinas@psi.ch and christian.bauer@psi.ch**Keywords:** marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR), prospective regionalized life cycle assessment (pRLCA), environmental trade-offs, climate change mitigation, ocean alkalinity enhancement, Nova Scotia, CanadaSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

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Abstract

Ocean alkalinity enhancement (OAE) is a promising marine carbon dioxide removal (CDR) option, but its net climate benefit and wider environmental implications depend strongly on where, and how it is implemented as well as on decarbonized energy and material supply chains. We develop a prospective, site-specific, life cycle assessment (pLCA) that couples a field trials' validated high-resolution ocean biogeochemical model with life cycle assessment for five OAE pathways deployed via wastewater outfalls in Halifax Harbor, Canada: three on magnesium hydroxide (two from serpentinite, via ammonium sulfate (AS) and HCl leaching (HCl), one from bischofite brine (BIS)) and two on sodium hydroxide (from industrial-grade sodium chloride (NaOHs) and seawater desalination brine hydroxide (NaOHb)). Using the functional unit of removing and permanently storing 1 t of atmospheric CO₂, we compare present-day conditions with a 2050 scenario and quantify eighteen ReCiPe 2016 midpoint impacts. Present-day results show little to no net climate benefit: net climate effects range from -0.09 to $+0.71$ t CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) per t CO₂ removed, with fossil electricity and heat supply dominating the impact. By 2050, all pathways are net removers with uptake efficiencies of 81%–95% as energy supply decarbonizes. BIS performs best in sixteen of eighteen impact categories, whereas NaOHs and AS are consistently worst across most categories. As energy decarbonizes, burdens shift from fossil fuel combustion to materials, metals, and related mining (especially copper), chemicals, and biofuels production for feedstock transport. The analysis shows that robust OAE assessment requires site-specific CO₂ uptake efficiencies, prospective supply-chain representation, and multi-criteria evaluation rather than focusing only on net CO₂ removal, because climate-attractive pathways can carry substantial burdens in (eco)toxicity, resource depletion, or other impact categories. The proposed coupling of a validated regional ocean model with pLCA provides a transferable template to evaluate OAE and other marine CDR options in CDR portfolios.

1. Introduction

The global ocean surface waters have warmed and acidified since the start of the industrial revolution. Surface warming leads to stronger stratification which results in fewer nutrients stirred up to the surface and reduced primary productivity and water

re-oxygenation (von Schuckmann *et al* 2024). Marine heatwaves have become more common and widespread increasing the risk for mass species loss, coral bleaching, harmful or toxic algal blooms, hypoxia, and rapid changes in which specific species dominate an ecosystem (Doney *et al* 2012, Feng *et al* 2024, von Schuckmann *et al* 2024). Looking forward,

studies that project future changes indicate that disturbances will intensify unless warming is decreased (Bryndum-Buchholz *et al* 2019, IPCC 2023). Recent evidence further suggests that future warming and elevated CO₂ can reduce the resistance, resilience, and recovery of coastal phytoplankton communities, making restoration more difficult under climate change (Chen *et al* 2026).

Keeping the global mean surface temperature increase well below 2 °C by 2100 relative to pre-industrial levels requires rapid, global deployment of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) (Lamb *et al* 2024) in combination with fast reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Theoretically, the world needs an annual global CO₂ removal rate of up to 10 Gt CO₂/yr by 2050 and around 20 Gt CO₂/yr by 2100 (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine 2019). A scale-up of this level of deployment depends on many factors that need to be evaluated beforehand, including resource needs and availability, environmental co-benefits and trade-offs, energy requirements, monitoring and verification, permanence of CO₂ removal, technology development, costs, and governance (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine 2019, Prütz *et al* 2024). These factors vary across technologies and regions and will also evolve over time.

Environmental life cycle assessment (LCA) is a methodological approach that helps evaluate and compare CDR technologies by quantifying their respective environmental co-benefits and trade-offs (side-effects), as well as energy and resource requirements (de Bruijn *et al* 2002, ISO 2006). LCA tracks the inputs and outputs of a product or service lifecycle—from the materials extraction and production to use and end-of-life treatment—and translates them into environmental impacts (de Bruijn *et al* 2002, ISO 2006). LCA is particularly useful during the design and pilot stages (low TRL technologies) because it can identify undesirable impacts, environmental hot-spots, or burden shifts early when design choices are still flexible, before they risk becoming locked in through large-scale deployment (Hetherington *et al* 2013).

In the case of CDR, it is known that a ‘climate beneficial’ performance can come with pressures concerning other environmental impact categories (Deutz and Bardow 2021, Briones-Hidrovo *et al* 2022) making it essential to ensure that they benefit climate change mitigation without worsening other aspects of human and ecosystem life (causing trade-offs).

LCA enables comparison of CDR options providing the same service/function on a technology-specific basis and identify where in the supply chain the co-benefits and side effects arise. Given the considerable differences in supply chains, feedstock choices, and application logistics across different

technologies, such detailed assessment is necessary to identify options that are robust across several environmental criteria, especially when considering future scenarios (Terlouw *et al* 2021a).

Although several LCA studies of CDR technologies exist, they do not capture the implications of simultaneous large-scale deployment under future climate scenarios (Bauer *et al* 2024, Matušík *et al* 2020, Terlouw *et al* 2021a, 2021b, Briones-Hidrovo *et al* 2022, Duval-Dachary *et al* 2023, Pratama *et al* 2023, Zhang *et al* 2023, Osman *et al* 2024). Before implementing such global assessments, the LCA framework must be better adapted to reflect the specificities of CDR (Nordahl *et al* 2024). In the case of CDR methods that imitate natural systems (ocean alkalinity enhancement (OAE), biochar application to soil (BAS), coastal enhanced rock weathering (ERW), seaweed farming etc), foreground system models must be coupled with biophysical models that represent the interaction between the CDR intervention and its receiving medium (i.e., land or water) (Joseph *et al* 2021, Zhou *et al* 2025). These interactions critically determine not only the effective CO₂ removal rate but also associated co-benefits and potential side effects, which current LCA practice does not adequately capture (Joseph *et al* 2021, Zhou *et al* 2025).

In this study, we focus specifically on the LCA of OAE. OAE refers to the enhancement of the ocean’s natural capacity for CO₂ uptake through the deliberate addition of alkaline substances (in particulate or liquid form) to seawater (Renforth and Henderson 2017, Eisaman *et al* 2023, Oschlies *et al* 2025). OAE’s main advantage compared to other marine CDRs (e.g. seaweed sinking, iron fertilization) is that it targets inorganic carbonate chemistry: added alkalinity increases the ocean’s capacity to hold carbon as dissolved bicarbonate and carbonate ions (Oschlies *et al* 2023) and is described as offering potentially thousands-of-years storage (Hartmann *et al* 2013). In principle, OAE can also raise pH and thereby ameliorate local ocean acidification (Oschlies *et al* 2023).

A characteristic that OAE shares with all other marine CDR technologies is that CO₂ removal is delayed by air–sea equilibration (months to years) and that biological impacts are poorly understood (Fennel 2026). A key disadvantage of OAE is that some mineral/industrial feedstocks may co-release trace elements/impurities (Oschlies *et al* 2023).

In OAE, added alkalinity does not translate instantly into atmospheric CO₂ removal but proceeds in a few steps (Fennel 2026), illustrated in figure 1:

1. An alkaline substance in particulate or liquid form is released into seawater. In the case of a particulate feedstock, dissolution occurs while particles sink (Wang *et al* 2025).

- The added alkalinity that is retained in the surface mixed layer, lowers seawater $p\text{CO}_2$ (partial pressure of carbon dioxide).
- While seawater with lowered $p\text{CO}_2$ resides in the surface mixed layer, a net flux of atmospheric CO_2 occurs into the ocean until re-equilibration is achieved. The pace of equilibration depends on gas transfer velocity, which in turn varies with local conditions, including wind speed, waves, temperature, salinity, and dissolved inorganic carbon concentration. A major fraction of equilibration occurs over a few weeks to several months (Wang *et al* 2023, Laurent *et al* 2026) while full equilibration can take years (He and Tyka 2023, Zhou *et al* 2025).
- Inefficiencies in the process include long-term loss of alkalinity from the surface mixed layer before re-equilibration is achieved and potential secondary precipitation of CaCO_3 , which would remove alkalinity (Hartmann *et al* 2023, Ringham *et al* 2024).

Because ‘alkalinity added’ does not linearly translate to ‘ CO_2 removed from air,’ LCAs should explicitly represent release location and hydrodynamic residence, advection and mixing, the time course of air–sea equilibration, feedstock formation and dissolution, and (if applicable) alkalinity losses to secondary mineral precipitation, biogenic calcium carbonate formation, or organic matter recycling (Fennel *et al* 2023).

Existing OAE LCAs have primarily quantified the supply-chain footprint of alkalinity production and spreading under simplified representations of ocean uptake or externally sourced, typically region-averaged ocean uptake efficiency factors rather than site-specific, validated ocean-model output (Foteinis *et al* 2022, 2023, Katish *et al* 2026). In this study, we address this first research gap by coupling a high-resolution regional ocean biogeochemical model, validated against field observations into the LCA foreground. This provides a site-specific, field-validated CO_2 uptake efficiency that reflects local circulation, stratification, carbonate chemistry, and equilibration timescales, and it is used consistently to size dosing and CO_2 removal in the life cycle inventory (LCI).

In parallel, recent methodological advances enable integrating socioeconomic pathways and climate scenarios into LCA via prospective background databases (Sacchi *et al* 2022). These databases represent future economies under different climate trajectories, thereby enhancing the validity of future assessments, which is important for assessing OAE implementation in the next decades. In practice, this means that the provision of electricity, fuels, industrial heat, materials production, and other necessary inputs for OAE implementation can be represented under future decarbonization trajectories. Recent prospective LCA work has begun integrating IAM-based scenarios into background databases, and initial OAE applications of prospective backgrounds are emerging (Katish *et al* 2026). Nevertheless, there

is room for improvement, as currently, the background scenarios do not reflect explicit marine CDR deployment constraints. Here, we address this second research gap by evaluating five OAE options under a 2050 background consistent with REMIND v3.5 under SSP2 (Strefler *et al* 2025), using a scenario set up that is aligned with OAE deployment assumptions and includes a precautionary global uptake constraint for marine alkalinity enhancement. This enables a prospective comparison of multiple OAE supply pathways in a background system that reflects future decarbonization trajectories relevant to deployment.

Lastly, the CO₂ uptake efficiency (η) expressed as the molar ratio of carbon uptake to total alkalinity added (mol C/mol TA), is state-dependent, varying with atmospheric pCO₂, temperature, and background carbonate chemistry, so CO₂ removed per unit alkalinity can differ in 2050 compared to today at the same site. Existing prospective OAE LCAs (Katish *et al* 2026) often hold η fixed over time or apply region-averaged factors without explicitly linking the TA to CO₂ removal to the chosen scenario trajectory. We address this third gap by explicitly updating η for 2050 using a carbonate-chemistry calculation parameterized with the atmospheric CO₂ concentration associated with the selected scenario. In this way, the TA to CO₂ removal translation in the LCI is both site-specific and consistent with the assumed scenario.

Taken together, these three methodological advances: site-specific, field-validated ocean modeling incorporated in LCA, a scenario-dependent prospective background that supports harmonized multi-pathway comparison under explicit OAE deployment constraints, and a scenario-consistent adjustment of η to future carbonate chemistry, provide a more comprehensive basis for assessing OAE that avoids treating ocean uptake, upstream supply chains, and deployment context in isolation.

2. Methodology

2.1. Goal and scope definition

The primary goal of this site-specific prospective, life cycle assessment is to quantify and compare current and future potential environmental impacts of five distinct OAE technologies removing and permanently storing atmospheric CO₂ in the ocean. Specifically, this analysis covers pathways of OAE involving (1) magnesium hydroxide (Mg(OH)₂) derived from serpentinite using ammonium sulfate, (2) Mg(OH)₂ produced via the Magnifin hydrochloric acid leaching process, (3) Mg(OH)₂ produced through the Aman process using bischofite brine, (4) sodium hydroxide (NaOH) derived via chlor-alkali electrolysis of industrial-grade sodium chloride and (5) NaOH produced via electrolysis of seawater desalination brine (see table 1). This methodological

approach aligns with ISO standards 14 040/14 044 (ISO 2006) and follows an attributional approach.

The functional unit is the removal and permanent storage of one ton (1 t) atmospheric CO₂. The geographical scope of this study is Nova Scotia (Canada), as this region has site-specific, validated CO₂ uptake efficiencies (Laurent *et al* 2026), thereby enhancing the representativeness and reliability of the results.

The system boundaries are illustrated in figure 2. They follow a consistent cradle-to-grave perspective where each pathway is modeled with the same four foreground modules: (i) alkalinity feedstock sourcing (wherever applicable), (ii) alkalinity production, (iii) dilution & dispersal via an existing wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) outfalls (same dispersing method as in the regionalized ocean model) (Laurent *et al* 2026), and (iv) atmospheric CO₂ uptake by air–sea re-equilibration and storage. When relevant, multifunctionality in foreground processes is addressed through economic allocation, as detailed in the supplementary information (SI).

Before dosing, all solids are prepared on-site as a 20 wt. % solution. We assume a distance of 100 km from the production site to the outfalls for all the pathways. In the CO₂ uptake unit process, the site-specific ocean-model-based factor η (mol C/mol TA) is integrated in the foreground system at the LCI model, ensuring that ‘TA dosed translated into CO₂ removed’ is model-informed, field-validated, and location-specific. More details on coupling are provided in the following subsection and the SI file.

The system boundaries do not account for potential losses of alkalinity due to secondary mineral precipitation of calcium carbonate. We assume the removal and storage of CO₂ is permanent or, in other words, we assume dosing of alkalinity feedstock is conducted safely via an alkaline solution under conditions designed to avoid precipitation (Hartmann *et al* 2023). This assumption is reasonable and consistent with the 2025 Halifax field trials, which are continuously monitored to avoid the initiation of secondary CaCO₃ precipitation and other alkalinity loss pathways under the credited operating conditions (Planetary Technologies 2025a, 2025b).

For the prospective background system, we use a 2050 scenario generated by the IAM REMIND v3.5 (Strefler *et al* 2025) alongside a present-day baseline. This scenario follows the SSP2 pathway (nicknamed ‘Middle of the Road’). It limits OAE deployment to exclusive economic zones, resulting in a maximum global CO₂ uptake of 5 Gt CO₂/yr. The foreground system remains unchanged in future scenarios.

Environmental impacts are quantified at the midpoint level using the ReCiPe 2016 v1.3 impact assessment method (Huijbregts *et al* 2016), and impact scores are calculated using the Brightway LCA framework (Mutel 2017). For the climate change impact category, results are reported as tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (t CO₂e) per ton of CO₂ removed.

Table 1. OAE systems under analysis and their abbreviations.

Alternative systems under analysis	Abbreviation
OAE using magnesium hydroxide produced from serpentinite rock treated with ammonium sulfate	AS
OAE using magnesium hydroxide produced from bischofite brine, a waste product from potash mining	BIS
OAE using magnesium hydroxide produced from serpentinite rock leached with hydrochloric acid	HCl
OAE using sodium hydroxide produced from seawater desalination brine	NaOHb
OAE using sodium hydroxide produced via chlor-alkali using industrial-grade sodium chloride	NaOHs

Carbon dioxide equivalent (CO_2e) expresses the combined climate warming effect of CO_2 and other greenhouse gases in a common unit (ISO 2018, IPCC 2022). In this study, climate change impacts are quantified using 100 year global warming potentials (GWP100), which express the warming effect of greenhouse gases over a 100 year time horizon (ISO 2018, IPCC 2022). Thus, $\text{t CO}_2\text{e}$ denotes climate change impact, whereas t CO_2 removed denotes the amount of atmospheric CO_2 removed and permanently stored.

From this point forward, the technological pathways will be referred to by their abbreviations, as listed in table 1.

2.2. Integrating a high-resolution regional ocean model's output into LCA foreground modeling

OAE studies usually report the carbon uptake per unit of added alkalinity which we denote here as η (mol C/mol TA). This oceanographic efficiency describes how much CO_2 is taken up per mole equivalent of

alkalinity that is successfully expressed in the surface ocean, independent of the specific reagent used (He and Tyka 2023, Palmiéri and Yool 2024).

CO_2 uptake resulting from the addition of dissolved feedstock at the Halifax Harbor outfall is calculated using a high-resolution regional model (Laurent *et al* 2026) combined with large-scale efficiency estimates from a global model (Zhou *et al* 2025) for the unequilibrated fraction of alkalinity leaving the regional domain (see SI).

Laurent *et al* (2026) simulated OAE in three locations in Halifax Harbor: Mill Cove, Tufts Cove, and Herring Cove. Since the three locations yield similar η values (0.8304, 0.8178, 0.7900) with a range of only 0.0404 mol C/mol TA (approx. 5% of the mean), for our case study we use their mean as a representative Halifax Harbor value ($\eta = 0.8127$).

The maximum achievable uptake η as previously mentioned is calculated from alkalinity (e.g. Zhou *et al* 2025, Laurent *et al* 2026). Therefore, given the same environmental conditions, OAE implemented

using NaOH and Mg(OH)₂ has the same η . However, for the LCA we require a mass-based CO₂ removal per unit of feedstock, which depends on η and on how much effective alkalinity a feedstock delivers to seawater. Since NaOH and Mg(OH)₂ provide different amounts of alkalinity ions (OH⁻) per unit mass, the mass-based CO₂ removal per unit mass of Mg(OH)₂ versus NaOH differs. It is the mass-based CO₂ removal that defines the dosing requirements in the LCI to remove 1 t CO₂ for each feedstock.

Lastly, we estimate the possible impact on η from changes in carbonate chemistry that may occur by 2050 using the box model described in Fennel (2026) parameterized with the atmospheric pCO₂ of the selected REMIND v3.5 SSP2 scenario.

For the detailed equations, parameter definitions, concrete examples, and the 2050 carbonate-chemistry adjustment, refer to SI.

2.3. Inventory analysis

The five pathways share similar foreground processes, from feedstock sourcing, alkalinity production, dilution and dispersion and finally CO₂ uptake. Nevertheless, they differ in alkalinity source, alkalinity production technology, and the amount of reagent required to meet the functional unit. As shown in figure 3, the AS and HCl pathways use serpentine rock as a feedstock, the BIS uses bischofite brine, NaOHs uses industrial-grade sodium chloride, and NaOHb uses seawater desalination brine. Alkalinity production technologies also differ in the types and amounts of inputs, energy, co-products, waste, and

emissions. The selected data sources for compiling our inventories represent the best available peer-reviewed information for each pathway and ensure that comparative LCA results reflect genuine differences in process technology rather than data quality artifacts. We note, however, that pathway-specific inventories for OAE relevant processes are still sparse and uneven in time coverage. Where multiple sources exist, we select the most ‘process representative’ and transparent datasets, and we account for data age and validity limitations through the uncertainty analysis (and point them out as a limitation in the discussion section). Where pathways generate co-products, burdens are allocated economically among the main alkaline product and the associated marketable co-products. In practice, this concerns iron oxyhydroxide in AS, sodium silicate in HCl, recovered acid and salt streams in BIS, and chlorine and hydrogen in the chlor-alkali pathways. Detailed unit process descriptions, data collection, mass/energy balances, inventory calculations, and allocation choices are provided in the SI.

2.4. Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis

We propagate foreground parametric uncertainty via Monte Carlo simulation with 5000 iterations, a run count within common LCA practice (Heijungs 2019). This was sufficient for our application to yield stable estimates of medians, 95% intervals, and rank-probability metrics. For each draw, we sample the assigned input distributions (e.g., lognormal, bounded triangular) and recompute LCIA results. We

summarize outputs as medians and 95% intervals and test ranking robustness using the probability of being best and pairwise win probabilities (see SI for details).

Following hotspot identification, we ran two targeted sensitivity analyses to test the drivers of the baseline hotspots. First, we shifted copper supply to a 100% recycled market to test whether virgin copper production is a key driver of the eutrophication, human toxicity, and ecotoxicity hotspots identified across OAE pathways. Second, we replaced copper smelting co-product routes in the sulfuric acid market while maintaining overall market mass balance to test whether the eutrophication, human toxicity, and ecotoxicity impacts of AS are driven by sulfuric acid sourced from copper smelting (see SI). We also tested the sensitivity of the results to changes in η to better understand how site-to-site differences in η affect outcomes.

3. Results

The following section focuses on the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results. We discuss climate change impacts first and then complement this analysis with other environmental impact categories.

3.1. Climate change impact

Here, net climate impact is calculated as life cycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions minus the CO₂ permanently stored. Under present conditions, the implementation of OAE technologies offers very little to no net CO₂ removal, resulting in net climate impacts of -0.09 (AS), -0.03 (BIS), $+0.16$ (HCl), $+0.71$ (NaOHb), and $+0.35$ (NaOHs) t CO₂e/t CO₂ removed (see figures 4 and 5). The primary reason is that fossil-fuel-based energy supply dominates life-cycle emissions. Coal-based electricity is the single largest driver across NaOHs and NaOHb (48%–51% of impacts), with additional burdens from lignite and natural gas-based electricity. For BIS and HCl, heat from natural gas used for alkalinity production exhibits the greatest impact (72%–73%), while for AS, the impact is caused by coal-based electricity and natural gas-based heat. Smaller but common contributors across technologies are fossil-based road freight, mining hard coal, oil and gas extraction, oil-based electricity, and coal-based heat.

In contrast, in 2050, we observe how all the pathways emit (substantially) less than what they remove, resulting in a net climate benefit with different magnitudes, mainly reflecting the dynamics of electricity and heat decarbonization. By 2050, all pathways become strong net removers: -0.918 (AS), -0.948 (BIS), -0.933 (HCl), -0.885 (NaOHb), and -0.924 (NaOHs) t CO₂e/t CO₂ removed. Despite the increase in electricity demand mainly due to electrification of heat (for AS, BIS, HCl, table 41 in SI), with electricity and heat largely decarbonized, the burden shifts

upstream to specific materials, chemicals, logistics, and infrastructure (figure 5). Detailed contribution analysis is available in the SI.

3.2. Environmental trade-offs

The environmental impacts for the remaining impact categories are reported per 1 t of net CO₂ removed, following emerging guidance for CDR LCA functional units (Butnar *et al* 2024). We present results for 2050 only, as three of the five pathways do not achieve net CO₂ removal under present conditions.

Regardless of the net climate benefits of all pathways in 2050 (figure 4), substantial trade-offs emerge across the remaining environmental impact categories (figure 6).

In the case of AS, although a strong net remover in 2050 (-0.92 t CO₂e), it exhibits the most notable trade-offs in acidification, mineral/metals depletion, particulate matter formation, all ecotoxicity categories, non-carcinogenic human toxicity, freshwater eutrophication, and water use. BIS, on the other hand, performs best across sixteen categories (including climate change) and second best for water use (second lowest after NaOHb) with a trade-off in ionizing radiation (second highest), indicating a favorable pathway in 2050 when compared to the rest of the OAE pathways. HCl exhibits a strong net climate benefit in 2050 and generally a low-to-mid impact across several impact categories. Nevertheless, HCl has two clear trade-offs: it ranks highest (worst) in ionizing radiation and ranks second highest in mineral/metals depletion and carcinogenic human toxicity (after AS and NaOHs, respectively). NaOHs also exhibits a strong net climate benefit in 2050 but with clear trade-offs concentrated in fossil energy demand, marine eutrophication, carcinogenic human toxicity, ozone depletion, and photochemical smog-related impact categories. As for NaOHb, it provides a strong climate benefit in 2050 and performs best in water use. The main trade-off concerns its land use as well as relatively high impact (second highest) in particulate matter formation, ozone depletion, acidification, and fossil fuel depletion.

The pattern behind the 2050 outcomes is consistent: metals and chemicals production, mining and its waste as well as infrastructure dominate the scores across technologies in most impact categories. These hotspots arise through different ‘pathway specific’ supply chains, such as renewable electricity infrastructure in BIS and HCl, chemical plant infrastructure in NaOHs and NaOHb, and sulfuric acid supply for Mg(OH)₂ production in AS as detailed in the next paragraph. Mining waste treatment (sulfidic tailings, lignite and hard coal mining spoil), copper production, metal waste and municipal solid waste incineration (MSWI) are major contributors to human toxicity (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) as well as freshwater and marine ecotoxicity. In the case of terrestrial ecotoxicity, besides copper and metal waste,

Figure 4. Analysis of climate change impact measured in kg CO₂e/t CO₂ removed. The green bar represents gross removal (i.e., -1000 kg CO₂, as defined by the functional unit). The purple overlay shows the life cycle GHG emissions from the complete OAE value chain to achieve that removal, and the dashed rectangle indicates the net climate impact, calculated as the life cycle GHG emissions minus the CO₂ permanently stored. Negative net emissions are equivalent to net removal.

transport brake wear emissions, PV cell manufacturing, ferronickel, and ferrochromium production are among the main contributors.

Mining tailings in this case are a consequence of ferrochromium, ferronickel (for steel making), and copper production, while metal waste from steel making is slag. Steel and copper needs arise from infrastructure for chemical plants (NaOHs, NaOHb) and for renewable electricity for electrified heat (BIS, HCl). In the case of AS, smelting copper is needed to supply sulfuric acid used for magnesium hydroxide production.

For energy depletion (fossil), oil and gas extraction dominates for all pathways, along with coal and lignite mining. Freshwater eutrophication is primarily caused by spoil and tailing treatment used for different purposes across pathways. They are linked to metal production in chemical plant infrastructure (NaOHs, NaOHb), to sulfuric acid production for magnesium hydroxide production in AS, and to renewable electricity infrastructure used for electrified heat for BIS and HCl. Marine eutrophication is mainly caused by wastewater treatment in sodium chloride (NaCl) production for NaOHs, NaOHb, and biofuel chains (from rapeseed production for diesel production, from willow production for electricity, and syngas production in BIS/HCl/NaOHs/NaOHb), as well as from ammonium sulfate production for AS.

In terrestrial acidification, hotspots differ across pathways: In AS, due to NH₃ emissions on-site from Mg(OH)₂ production, in NaOHb, due to sulfur dioxide (SO₂) used for dechlorination, soda ash production used for chemical softening, copper production

for chemical plants infrastructure, and rapeseed production used for biofuels. In NaOHs, due to copper production used in infrastructure and rapeseed cultivation with smaller shares of mining, blasting, soda ash, and quicklime (for sodium chloride production), sulfuric acid (for the chlor-alkali process), as well as coal-based heat, glass production, aluminum (for chemical plants infrastructure), and road freight. In HCl and BIS, copper production is for renewable electricity infrastructure (for electrified heat), blasting is used in mining for serpentinite, rapeseed cultivation, coal-based heat, with smaller shares of aluminum, glass production (renewable electricity infrastructure), clinker, sulfuric acid, nylon, and lignite-based electricity.

Photochemical oxidants formation is primarily caused by serpentinite mining/blasting, road/sea freight, and (for AS) Mg(OH)₂ production due to NH₃ emissions on site. HCl and BIS add glass production, electricity production from biomass, diesel, and hydrogen. Particulate matter formation is primarily caused by copper production, mining activities, coal-based heat, ferrochromium and aluminum production, as well as clinker, rapeseed cultivation, nylon, and sulfuric acid production (HCl, NaOHs, BIS). NaOHb adds SO₂ and soda ash production, while AS Mg(OH)₂ production is due to NH₃ emissions on site. The main contributors to land-use impacts are rapeseed, willow production (for biofuels for transportation), and infrastructure. Material depletion occurs due to the use of rare earth elements in NaCl production and deionized water supply chains, metals production for electrified heating, and serpentinite

Figure 5. Contribution analysis for climate change impacts (the positive emissions in figure 4) across five OAE technologies and two scenarios: Present (2025) and a future (2050) scenario. The stacked bars represent the main contributors per technology responsible for 63%–82% of the impact.

mining (HCl/AS). Water use is dominated by renewable electricity production (for BIS, HCl, NaOHs, NaOHb), Mg(OH)₂ production (AS), and the chlor-alkali process (NaOHs).

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

Our sensitivity analysis results show that if we were to meet the demand for copper by recycled means, some impact categories (FET, FE, HTNC, MET, PMF, AC, TET) see a reduction that spans from −13.7% to −14.3% for AS, −21.4% to −47.2% for BIS and HCl, −12.2% to −57.9% for NaOHs and −11.6% to −25.7% for NaOHb (see table 2). Some of the largest reductions for NaOHs include reductions of

−57.9% in FET, −55.7% in MET, −54.7% in HTNC, −49.4% in MD, and −44.9% in FE. BIS and HCl show a similar pattern, with reductions of −46.9% and −47.2% in HTNC, −40.7% and −37.4% in MD, and −39.4% and −40.1% in FET, respectively. In the case of NaOHb the largest reductions are observed in FET (−25.7%), FE (−24.2%), and MET (−23.5%).

Similarly, our sensitivity analysis shows that if the sulfuric acid required for AS is produced via processes that do not use copper smelting, AS specific impacts (FET, FE, HTNC, MET, AC, TET) decrease by 15.8% to 70% (see table 3). For AS the largest reductions occur in HTNC (−70.6%), MET (−59.4%), FET (−58.9%), FE (−56.7%), and TET (−51.4%).

Figure 6. 2050 OAE scenario small-multiple plots of 17 environmental impact categories per 1 t net CO₂ removed, shown as min–max normalized values (0–1) within each impact category. In each panel, the impacts of five OAE technologies (AS, BIS, HCl, NaOHs, NaOHb) are scaled such that the lowest technology-specific value equals 0 and the highest equals 1, preserving the within-category ranking while enabling comparison of relative differences across technologies. Normalized values are not comparable across impact categories in absolute magnitude. They indicate relative performance within each category. Impact category abbreviations: AC—acidification, terrestrial (kg SO₂-eq); FET—ecotoxicity, freshwater (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); MET—ecotoxicity, marine (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); TET—ecotoxicity, terrestrial (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); ER—energy resources, non-renewable, fossil (kg oil-eq); FE—eutrophication, freshwater (kg P-eq); ME—eutrophication, marine (kg N-eq); HTC—human toxicity, carcinogenic (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); HTNC—human toxicity, non-carcinogenic (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); IR—ionizing radiation (kg Co-60-eq); LU—land use (m²·a crop-eq); MD—material resources, metals/minerals (kg Cu-eq); OD—ozone depletion (kg CFC-11-eq); PMF—particulate matter formation (kg PM_{2.5}); POF_H—photochemical oxidant formation, human health (kg NO_x-eq); POF_T—photochemical oxidant formation, terrestrial ecosystems (kg NO_x-eq); WU—water use (m³ water).

Table 2. Sensitivity analysis when using recycled copper. The values reflect the percentage (%) change in impact from the baseline. Negative represents reduction while positive increase in impact. Values in bold represent significant reductions of impacts.

Technology	LU	ER	FET	FE	CC	HTC	HTNC	IR	MET	ME	OD	PMF	POF_T	POF_H	MD	AC	TET	WU
AS	-1.3	-0.4	-14.3	-13.7	-0.7	-2.3	-13.6	-0.5	-14.3	-0.3	-2.7	-0.4	-4.2	-4.3	0.0	-0.2	-6.8	0.0
BIS	-1.0	-0.6	-39.4	-23.7	-0.6	-1.4	-46.9	-0.1	-37.8	-1.0	-2.6	-34.7	-8.6	-8.8	-10.5	-40.7	-21.4	-0.1
HCl	-0.9	-0.6	-40.1	-23.5	-0.6	-1.4	-47.2	-0.2	-38.6	-0.9	-2.4	-29.7	-6.0	-6.2	0.0	-37.4	-23.2	-0.1
NaOHs	-1.7	-1.2	-57.9	-44.9	-1.4	-3.3	-54.7	-1.2	-55.7	-0.9	-0.7	-44.6	-12.2	-12.5	-0.9	-49.4	-25.9	-0.5
NaOHb	-0.4	-0.4	-25.7	-24.2	-0.6	-2.0	-15.8	-0.5	-23.5	-0.3	-0.7	-6.7	-5.3	-5.5	-5.5	-6.4	-11.6	-0.4

Table 3. Sensitivity analysis when we do not source sulfuric acid from smelting copper. The values reflect the percentage (%) change in impact from the baseline. Negative represents reduction while positive increase in impact. Values in bold represent significant reductions of impacts.

Technology	LU	ER	FET	FE	CC	HTC	HTNC	IR	MET	ME	OD	PMF	POF_T	POF_H	MD	AC	TET	WU
AS	-5.7	4.9	-58.9	-56.7	3.9	-6.0	-70.6	0.17	-59.4	-1.2	-8.8	0.07	-15.1	-15.6	-0.2	0.1	-51.4	0.5

Impact category abbreviations: AC—acidification, terrestrial (kg SO₂-eq); FET—ecotoxicity, freshwater (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); MET—ecotoxicity, marine (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); TET—ecotoxicity, terrestrial (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); ER—energy resources, non-renewable, fossil (kg oil-eq); FE—eutrophication, freshwater (kg P-eq); ME—eutrophication, marine (kg N-eq); HTC—human toxicity, carcinogenic (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); HTNC—human toxicity, non-carcinogenic (kg 1,4-DCB-eq); IR—ionizing radiation (kg Co-60-eq); LU—land use (m²·a crop-eq); MD—material resources, metals/minerals (kg Cu-eq); OD—ozone depletion (kg CFC-11-eq); PMF—particulate matter formation (kg PM_{2.5}); POF_H—photochemical oxidant formation, human health (kg NO_x-eq); POF_T—photochemical oxidant formation, terrestrial ecosystems (kg NO_x-eq); WU—water use (m³ water).

Table 4. Uncertainty analysis results comparing BIS to other pathways by impact category.

Impact category	P(best) top 1	P(best) top 2
CC	BIS 96.6%	HCl 3.4%
AC	BIS 95.6%	HCl 4.4%
FET	BIS 89.0%	HCl 11.0%
MET	BIS 88.8%	HCl 11.2%
TET	BIS 78.4%	HCl 21.6%
ER	BIS 97.2%	HCl 2.8%
FE	BIS 94.2%	HCl 5.8%
ME	BIS 99.4%	HCl 0.6%
HTC	BIS 62.8%	NaOHb 18.2%
HTNC	BIS 88.7%	HCl 11.3%
IR	NaOHb 95.3%	AS 4.7%
LU	BIS 96.8%	AS 2.3%
MD	BIS100.0%	AS 0.0%
OD	BIS 99.7%	HCl 0.3%
PMF	BIS 98.2%	HCl 1.8%
POF_H	BIS100.0%	HCl 0.0%
POF_T	BIS100.0%	HCl 0.0%
WU	NaOHb 100.0%	AS 0.0%

These are considerable reductions which highlight how tightly OAE's environmental footprint is coupled with broader industrial systems. Although OAE is a carbon removal technology, it is not isolated from the burdens associated with upstream supply chains. Therefore, these results also reinforce the added value of using LCA for CDR assessments: it helps identify such leverage points (e.g., promoting metal recycling or cleaner sulfuric acid production in this case) to mitigate upstream burdens.

3.4. Uncertainty analysis

Across the eighteen midpoint categories for the 2050 results, BIS achieved the lowest median impact in sixteen out of eighteen categories. NaOHb had the lowest median impact in the remaining two categories: IR and WU. HCl was typically the second-best performer by median in many categories, while AS and NaOHs most frequently occupied the lower ranks (higher impacts) depending on the indicator (see SI).

While median results suggest a clear overall winner, the robustness of 'BIS is best' varies strongly by impact category once uncertainty is propagated. Here, P(best) represents the probability that a pathway has the lowest impact in a given category across Monte Carlo iterations. The results (table 4) confirm that BIS is best in $\geq 95\%$ of MC iterations ($P(\text{best}) \geq 0.95$) for ten out of sixteen of the impact categories (where BIS performed best before propagating uncertainty). BIS is likely to stay the best in another four additional impact categories (best in 85%–95% of MC iterations). Not very likely for BIS to stay best for the remaining two impact categories (BIS is best in $< 85\%$ of MC iterations, meaning indicating some potential rank switching with the closest competitor).

4. Discussion

4.1. OAE's climate performance depends on decarbonized energy systems

Our results demonstrate that the net climate benefit of OAE is highly dependent on energy system context. Under current conditions, our OAE pathways provide little to no net CO₂ removal benefits, with fossil fuels accounting for 50%–73% of total GHG emissions. But by 2050, once electricity and heat may have decarbonized, all OAE pathways become net removers, with an estimated 81%–95% net carbon removal efficiency. Overall, with a clean energy supply, OAE's net climate performance is competitive with other CDR approaches in line with Katish *et al* (2026).

This performance is comparable to other CDR options under decarbonized conditions: 79%–93% for direct air carbon capture and storage (DACCS) (Deutz and Bardow 2021, Terlouw *et al* 2021b), 75%–95% for ERW (Lefebvre *et al* 2019, Eufrazio *et al* 2022, Foteinis *et al* 2023, Zhang *et al* 2023), 85%–93% for BAS (Muñoz *et al* 2017).

4.2. Upstream supply chain burdens and environmental trade-offs

On the other hand, our study shows that the impact of a certain technology on climate change alone cannot define environmental sustainability. The results across the eighteen impact categories suggest that no single OAE pathway is clearly superior across all environmental dimensions in 2050. Although these pathways provide a strong net climate benefit in 2050, they exhibit trade-offs across non-climate categories (which vary by pathway). Nevertheless, there is a clear pattern behind these trade-offs. Once electricity and

heat are largely low-carbon, impacts are no longer driven by energy combustion but by upstream industrial supply chains, particularly metals and chemicals production, mining and mining waste management, transport, and infrastructure development in line with Katish *et al* (2026). As a result, toxicity/ecotoxicity and several air- and resource-related categories are largely governed by the material intensity of plants and renewable-energy systems (and their associated copper/steel and waste flows), while eutrophication, land use, and air-quality indicators increasingly reflect biofuel/biomass and transport chains. For instance, the electrification of heat in the BIS and HCl pathways eliminates direct CO₂ emissions but comes with an embedded cost: it requires substantial infrastructure (renewable power generation, transmission capacity, etc), which in turn entails steel, copper, concrete, land use, and so on. In short, decarbonization makes OAE climatically effective, but it also exposes a second sustainability constraint: its reliance on the material and extractive economy. These shifts are consistent with LCA literature on CDR. Studies confirm that copper production for decarbonized DACCS/renewables increases terrestrial ecotoxicity by 2100 (Qiu *et al* 2022) while coastal ERW poses marine ecotoxicity risks from nickel releases (Foteinis *et al* 2023). Decarbonizing the grid yields only modest reductions in specific midpoint categories like acidification or toxicity, because those are increasingly driven by mining operations and material processing rather than fuel combustion (Eufrazio *et al* 2022, Qiu *et al* 2022, Hahn Menacho *et al* 2025a, Hahn Menacho *et al* 2025b). Similarly, transport distance has been identified as a critical factor for ERW: long-haul transport of minerals can offset net CO₂ benefits while sourcing rock locally minimizes emissions (Strefler *et al* 2018, Lefebvre *et al* 2019, Beerling *et al* 2020).

4.3. Mitigation opportunities for reducing upstream burdens

Our analysis also highlights opportunities to mitigate OAE's environmental trade-offs in the upstream supply chain. Prospective LCA studies on metal recovery and copper recycling reveal that secondary metals have considerable mitigation potential regarding climate change, terrestrial and freshwater ecotoxicity, human toxicity, and abiotic resource depletion due to the avoidance of sulfidic tailings production (Mehr *et al* 2021, Adrianto and Pfister 2022, Adrianto *et al* 2023). Our study supports these findings, showing that sourcing copper from recycling rather than virgin mining can reduce impacts by 12%–58% across FET, FE, AC, TET, HTNC, MET, and PMF for our OAE pathways. This is a direct co-benefit of a circular economy approach, which not only conserves resources

but also avoids the pollution associated with mining and smelting.

Site selection also matters. Our sensitivity analysis (see table 33, in SI) shows that in 2025, if η is high, systems perform far better. If η drops, 2025 outcomes deteriorate sharply, especially for NaOH-based routes. By 2050, decarbonizing heat and power largely reduces this sensitivity but choosing sites with high η still improves results. This also means that if countries do not decarbonize to SSP2 levels by 2050, selecting high η regions becomes non-negotiable for achieving net-negative emissions.

In a nutshell, from a real-world perspective, optimizing supply chain geography (using local alkaline sources or operations near coasts to reduce transport distances), choosing sites with a high η , and integrating circular economy measures (recycling metals, repurposing waste streams) will be as crucial as energy decarbonization for minimizing OAE's overall environmental footprint.

4.4. Uncertainty and robustness of the LCIA results rankings

Uncertainty propagation supports the robustness of the central comparative finding: BIS remains best in most categories across most Monte Carlo iterations, while also identifying where rankings are least stable. The least robust categories are typically toxicity-related, in which inventory and characterization uncertainties are known to be higher. This pattern is consistent with the known sensitivity of toxicity-related midpoints to inventory representation of emissions and to 'fate to exposure to effect' modeling assumptions (Huijbregts *et al* 2000, Rosenbaum *et al* 2008, 2011, Henderson *et al* 2011).

It is therefore critical to distinguish parameter uncertainty (captured here by Monte Carlo propagation of modeled input distributions) from uncertainty due to methodological choices. We interpret P(best) as a robustness measure conditional on the modeled foreground uncertainties, rather than as a classical hypothesis test of 'significance,' consistent with recent methodological discussions in comparative LCA.

4.5. Limitations and future research needs

Finally, we acknowledge some limitations of this study. First, OAE is deployed in the ocean, so it can also have local receiving-environment effects because alkalinity addition alters carbonate chemistry near the release point. These site-specific ecological responses and monitoring constraints are not captured by standard midpoint LCIA methods and are therefore not quantified here. In particular, our LCA does not represent potential OAE-induced changes in

plankton community composition, calcifier performance, or microbial biogeochemistry, which experimental, mesocosm, and synthesis studies indicate can be context-dependent and, in some cases, nonlinear (Ferderer *et al* 2022, Marín-Samper *et al* 2024, Sánchez *et al* 2024, Xin *et al* 2024, Antoni *et al* 2025, Bednaršek *et al* 2025, Guo *et al* 2025, Kesner *et al* 2025, Gropelli *et al* 2026). Addressing them would require coupling to ecological impact models and long-term monitoring data (Delval *et al* 2025, Oschlies *et al* 2025). Second, our analysis is geographically specific. We modeled OAE in a single location, whereas OAE performance depends strongly on local circulation, surface residence time, and air–sea gas exchange. In lower efficiency regions such as the Weddell and Ross Seas, deep winter mixing can move excess alkalinity out of the surface layer before much air–sea equilibration takes place (Zhou *et al* 2025). As a result, the same pathway would remove less CO₂ per unit of alkalinity and likely lead to higher upstream burdens per ton of net CO₂ removed than in Halifax. These regions are likely to be less favorable for OAE implementation. Particularly efficient, according to Zhou *et al* (2025), are the northwest North Atlantic, where Halifax is located, and the northeast Pacific. Third, our future scenario assumes specific technology and policy conditions that are uncertain. In addition to this, the background datasets used to represent future technologies are still evolving and may not fully capture process and supply-chain changes for metal/mining and waste treatment sectors which may affect the interpretation of results across several impact categories. Although the selected data sources for compiling our inventories represent the best available peer-reviewed information for each pathway as of today, we note, however, that pathway-specific LCIs for OAE relevant processes are still sparse and uneven in time coverage. These sources of uncertainty mean our quantitative results should be interpreted as scenario-based estimates rather than precise predictions.

Future research should prioritize: (i) expanding OAE LCA globally to diverse regions and ocean conditions, (ii) including ecosystem responses and long-term ocean monitoring data to validate modeled CO₂ uptake, (iii) developing integrated assessment frameworks that incorporate CDR options at scale, including economic and policy constraints, (iv) performing global large scale OAE implementation of prospective LCAs comparing a larger variety of feedstocks and technologies across different regions, (v) developing additional LCIs for OAE relevant unit processes in close collaboration with industry and (vi) developing sector-complete prospective background inventories, covering mining/metals and waste treatment.

Despite the limitations, the methodological advance of coupling a dynamic ocean model with

prospective LCA represents a meaningful step forward. It provides a more robust foundation for assessing marine CDR technologies under real-world conditions, and for designing evidence-based deployment strategies that maximize carbon removal while mitigating environmental trade-offs. This approach can be extended to other CDR methods to ensure that, as we scale up carbon removal, we do so with a holistic understanding of environmental outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This study advances the environmental LCA of OAE by coupling regionally validated ocean biogeochemical modeling with prospective LCA, transforming ‘alkalinity added’ to ‘atmospheric CO₂ removed’ under site-specific and future deployment conditions. Overall, our analysis shows that OAE’s performance as a climate solution will improve dramatically with a clean energy transition, achieving high net CO₂ removal efficiencies by mid-century. However, taking into consideration the trade-offs that the OAE pathways exhibit regardless of the climate mitigation potential they offer, the focus of environmental assessments must broaden, from simply maximizing carbon removal to managing the material and ecological implications of removing that carbon. By anticipating these shifts (e.g., metal supply bottlenecks, mining impacts, transport logistics) now, strategies like OAE can be developed more responsibly and effectively for the coming decades. For policy and deployment in settings comparable to the assessed site, three points for guidance follow directly from the results:

1. Implement OAE using decarbonized electricity and heat throughout the supply chain
2. Prioritize high-uptake-efficiency sites and avoid low-efficacy regions, and
3. Pair implementation with circular economy and transportation measures (e.g., high metal recycling rates, reduced transport distances, and waste-stream valorization) to mitigate upstream mining and infrastructure burdens.

The integration of site-specific ocean modeling with prospective LCA offers a template for such forward-looking assessments, helping ensure that carbon removal deployments are not only climatically effective but also environmentally sustainable across multiple criteria. Future work should extend this coupled framework to additional regions and pathways, improve inventory detail for foreground and

background inventories and toxicity-relevant emissions, explore upscaling to broader deployment contexts, as well as investigate ecosystem feedbacks.

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Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

OAE pLCA Supplementary Data available at <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ae5a4e/data1>.

Ethics statement

The authors declare that there are no ethical issues resulting from this study.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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